

**ACQUAINTING STUDENTS WITH THE LIFE AND WORKS OF MEDIEVAL AZERBAIJANI
PHILOSOPHERS (BAHMANYAR AL AZERBAIJANI, NASIREDDIN TUSI) IN PHYSICS
EDUCATION IN GRADES VII-IX**

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ABSTRACT

Teaching the pedagogic heritage of medieval Azerbaijani philosophers in physics education in grades VII-IX has unlimited potential in the education and upbringing of the young generation. The study of the heritage of these philosophers gives a wide opportunity to create a single didactic system, to form a highly spiritual personality, to have a differential influence on the characteristics of students, which confirms the creative use of the educational potential of a person and the instillation of humanistic education in the teacher, and to the socialization of the personality aimed at universal values. Some aspects of the topic of the problem analyzed in the article were addressed to philosophical thought. The investigated problem was studied in terms of formation, development and modernity of classical, non-classical and post-non-classical scientific paradigms. The relevance of the research topic, the innovations achieved in the processing of the problem determine its scientific and theoretical importance. The article mentions that in the Middle Ages, great achievements were made in the fields of science, philosophy, literature and art in the Muslim East. Philosophers who lived and worked in this period, wrote valuable works of scientists that contributed to the development of the science of physics, and took a unique position.

Keywords: teaching of physics, philosophy, training, methodology.

Teaching the creativity of Bahmanyar Al Azerbaijani to students in physics education

There are prominent scientists, artists, calligraphers, poets, musicians, commanders, statesmen and religious figures of ancient and medieval Azerbaijan, about whom most of us either know little or are unaware of their existence. True, this information was hidden from the people by the Soviet regime for many years, and those who were revealed were presented as representatives of another nation. Even today, we do not have extensive information about them. Our next study is about the prominent follower of Ibn Sina - Abu-l-Hasan Bahmanyar al-Azerbaijani. In history, there are traces of such scientists and powerful personalities that we are proud of those names and signatures. The services of Bahmanyar, one of the pioneers of Azerbaijani philosophical thought, are priceless. According to historical sources, Abulhasan Bahmanyar is one of the outstanding representatives of Azerbaijani-Eastern Peripateticism, the founder of the Azerbaijani philosophical school. It is mentioned that he was a student of Ibn Sina. The birthplace of the genius philosopher is unknown. However, the philosopher is usually mentioned in the sources as "al-Azerbaijani" and it is emphasized that he is from Azerbaijan. His student Zahiruddin al-Beyhaqi especially mentions that the philosopher is from Azerbaijan. Some sources state that he was formerly a Zoroastrian and later converted to Islam. Bahmanyar Azerbaijan, like most Eastern peripatetics, wrote his works in Arabic. The philosopher, whose creativity is of great importance not only in Azerbaijan, but in the history of Eastern philosophy in general, also created his own school with the valuable scientists he trained. (5)

Referring to historical sources, we can say that Abulhasan Bahmanyar lived a little less than thirty years after Ibn Sina. The stage of Eastern Peripateticism in the middle of the 11th century is directly related to his name. Preserving the traditions of Ibn Sina imposed

serious and responsible duties on the philosopher": He had to spare no effort to ensure the further development of Aristotelian philosophy. Perhaps with this hope, Ibn Sina once wrote about his beloved student Bahmanyar: "Bahmanyar gave ample space for quotations from Ibn Sina's works in his work, and tried to promote his teacher's ideas to a greater extent." The following works of Bahmanyar are mentioned in sources and sources: "Tahsil" ("at-Tahsil"), "Zinet on Logic" ("az-Zina fi-l-mantiq"), "Beauty" ("al-Bahja"), "Bliss" ("as-Saada"), "The Book of Music" ("Kitab fi-l-musiqqa"), "The Subject of Metaphysics" ("Maudu ilm ma bad at-tabi'ah"), "Floors of Existence" ("Maratib al-maujudat"). According to researchers, the work "Education" occupies a special place in Bahmanyar's creativity. The philosopher dedicated this work to his uncle Abu Mansur Bahram ibn Khurshid ibn Izadyar. Manuscript copies of its Arabic original, copied in different years, are stored in the manuscript funds of the libraries of Rampur, Tehran, Istanbul, Vatican City, Cairo, London and Beirut. "Tahsil" was first published in 1971 in Tehran.

According to the structure of this work, written as a result of his arguments with Ibn Sina, Bahmanyar notes in the preface that the meaning of the "Book of Knowledge" corresponds to all the works of his teacher. The educational work consists of three books: "Logic" ("al-Mantiq"), "Metaphysics" ("Elm ma bad at-tabiya") and "States of visible existing things" ("Ahval ayan al-maujudat"). These represent the mainly theoretical part of Eastern Peripateticism. In addition to Aristotle, the author mentions the names of Empedocles, Euclid, Socrates, Plato and other great scientists of antiquity and quotes them. He consistently followed the path of his teacher, benefiting from Ibn Sina's works and ideas in general in setting and solving important philosophical problems. "Education" was one of the important sources for the study of logic, metaphysics and nature in the Middle Ages. The prominent Arab philosopher Abdullatif Baghdadi (1163-1231) specifically noted

that he studied from this book, along with other works on Peripatetism. (3)

"Teaching of existence - essential and possible existence" is taught to students

In Bahmanyar's metaphysics, the degree of superiority of concepts is determined based on the volume. From this point of view, the concept of "existence" with the widest scope and the greatest generality is considered superior. In the book "Education" it is stated that "it is impossible to give a logical definition to the being. So, it is more primitive in the imagination, because it has neither a gender nor a distinguishing sign. In short, there is nothing more important to identify the being." Being viewed from different perspectives is essential and possible, cause and effect, primary and emergent, etc. divided into parts. The classification of existence in terms of its division into necessary and possible parts occupies an important place in the anthology of all Eastern peripatetics. Necessary or essential existence is the basis of existence, everything that exists apart from it is considered a possible existence. Bahmanyar, examining the parts of existence in their mutual form, writes that "essential existence is an existence whose non-existence cannot be assumed". Possible existence is necessary neither in existence nor in non-existence. The philosopher thereby confirms the idea that "a necessary being is a being without a cause in itself, because if it had a cause in its own existence, the being would exist with that cause. Then it would not be a necessary being in itself. A possible being is a being that is considered possible by its own essence. Such that its presence and absence are for a reason". Abunaser Farabi showed that possible existence is possible in itself, and necessary because of essential existence. This provision was accepted by Ibn Sina, Bahmanyar and later Peripatetics. Bahmanyar used the terms "uncaused existence", "first cause", "single" about the essential existence. The Arabic-speaking Peripatetics were deeply interested in the question of the first cause and its effect, and built their anthological teachings on this foundation. From this point of view, Yakub Kindi valued the science of the first cause as "the first philosophy". Bahmanyar, who imagines the whole existence as a cause and effect, wrote: "One of the two things we face is a cause, and the other is a result." All the Eastern Peripatetics agreed on the proposition of essential existence without essence. According to them, there is no substantial essence at the basis of necessary existence. In this regard, Bahmanyar writes: "It is not true that there is an essence that considers the importance of being necessary for an important being in itself. Then that importance in being would have to depend on that essence and not be important without it... In this case, the important being would not be important, because what is important for it there is a reason. This is impossible. Therefore, there is no essence for the essential being." According to Bahmanyar, essence is only for possible existence. Essential being first produces the essence of substance, and then the others. (6)

In the book "Education" it is said: "Everything that has an essence is a result". This idea is repeated in the same way in the book "Izahat". The widespread distribution of these works throughout the eastern world

shows the popularity of Bahmanyar at that time. Their faces were copied and distributed in various university and palace libraries. Among those works, the most famous are "Idrak", "Azzina" ("Decoration"), "Al-behja wa-s-saada" ("Joy and happiness"), "Fil-musiga" ("About Music") and others. These books, which have been copied and distributed, are kept in almost all major libraries of the world to this day. These works have been translated into European languages since the last century. Some of Bahmanyar's books were translated into Persian almost during his lifetime. The work "At-Tahsil" was translated into Russian by the well-known orientalist AB Sagadeyev and published in Baku in 1983 in three volumes. Bahmanyar is one of the scholars who created his own philosophical school. His scientific and educational activity played an important role in the development and spread of scientific and philosophical thought in Azerbaijan, as well as in the whole East. The brightest figure among his students was the great Khorasan philosopher and poet Abulabbas al-Lawkari. Bahmanyar's researchers trace Bahmanyar's inextricable ties to Nasir al-Din Tusi's school through the works of Al-Lawkari and his famous student Abulfat ibn Khayyam. Shihab al-Din al-Marjani, known as an educator and researcher in the history of Muslim culture, mentions Bahmanyar's name among the four most prominent luminaries of the East when talking about the history of philosophy: "Among them, the most famous and greatest are Abu Nasr al-Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Ghazi Abul Walid Muhammad Ibn Ahmad Ibn Rushd and Bahmanyar Ibn Al-Marzwan" (3).

Instilling the creativity of Nasireddin Tusi to students

Khaja Muhammad Nasreddin Tusi was born on February 17, 1201 (597 AH) in the city of Tus in the family of a teacher. The thinker's real name is Muhammad, his father's name is Muhammad, and his grandfather's name is Hasan. The people gave him the name Nasreddin because he was an intelligent, knowledgeable and outstanding scientist of his time. He adopted the nickname Tusi because he was born in the city of Tus.

According to its origin, it is originally from the city of Hamedan, which is considered one of the oldest cities of Azerbaijan. Nasreddin Tusi received his first education from his father Muhammad ibn Hasan. In his youth, he visited a number of large cities in the Near and Middle East in order to increase his knowledge. The thinker described his childhood in the preface of his work "Seyr va leech" and wrote: "When I was still a child, my father sent me to study with his friend, the mathematician Kamaledin Muhammad. Not long ago, my teacher went on a trip. I also visited a number of cities in consideration of my father's will. Whatever subject I found a teacher from, I took lessons from him. However, I must also say that I was particularly interested in theology and philosophy." (5)

Traveling around a number of cities of the East, Tusi met and learned from a number of prominent scholars of the time, including Fariduddin Damadla and Qutbuddin Misri, in the city of Nishapur.

The comprehensive and deep knowledge he received made Muhammad famous in the scientific environment in a short time. At the age of thirty, the leader of the Kuhistan Ismailis, Nasreddin Mohtasham, invited him to his palace and asked the young scholar to write a book on morality. In 1235, Nasreddin Tusi completed the famous work "Akhlaqi-Nasiri", which later brought him world fame and was translated into several languages. However, the ruler did not like the book and Tusi was arrested and taken to the "Alamut" fortress. He lives in exile here. Tusi, who was deprived of the right to leave the castle, was able to write several scientific works despite the unbearable spiritual hardships he spent with the Ismailis for more than 12 years. At the end of his famous work "Sharhul-Isharat", which was completed in 1242, the scientist writes: "I wrote most of these under the most difficult conditions. Rather, I wrote and compiled them at a time when every part of them cost me great pain and suffering. In that place, the fire of hell was always burning and boiling water was poured from above. There was not a time when my eyes were not filled with tears, and my heart was not filled with sorrow, and there was not an hour that did not increase my hardships, and there was not a minute that did not bring me new excitement. Yes, one of the Persian poets rightly said: "No matter how much I look around, I see the disaster in the form of a ring, and I am a precious gem located in the middle of that ring." "There was never a time in my life when he was not exposed to the horrors of fate, despair and sadness. Care has been the ruler of my eternal pleasure, and excitement its soldier. Oh God! Save me from the foothold of the host of misfortune and the nest of suffering.

In 1253, Genghis Khan's grandson Hulaku Khan's campaign to the Middle East begins. His troops occupy the fortress of Alamut, which is considered impregnable, and free Nasreddin and other scholarly prisoners. Nasreddin Hulaku Khan's personal adviser is appointed. Tusi has been thinking about the observatory for a long time. As soon as Baghdad was taken, Nasreddin asked the Khan for permission to build an observatory.

While discussing the issue of building the famous Maragha observatory, Hulaku-khan asked the prominent mathematician and astronomer Nasreddin Tusi, what is the need for such an expense, what will be the benefit of the observatory to be built? Without giving any answer, Tusi invites the ruler to walk near the city and orders them to throw down a copper pot from the top of the mountain towards the road. When the cauldron was coming, it made a huge noise and those who heard this sound ran in panic and tried to save their lives. And Tusi said Hulaku-khan:(2)

- We know the reason for this incident, which scared everyone, and we were sitting quietly. Also, in order to live peacefully on earth, it is necessary to study the events in the sky.

The establishment of the observatory required a large sum of money. The well-known historian Haji Khalifa describes the events in his "Book of the World" as follows: "When Khaja Nasreddin told Hulaku about the expenses needed to start the construction of the astronomical observatory in the cave, he doubted the

magnitude of the amount: "That is, the science of the stars is so useful that shall we spend so much money on the observatory?" Nasir replied: "Allow a person to climb that mountain and drop an empty bowl from there, but do it in such a way that no one knows." And so they do. The stone makes a scary sound as it hits the rocks. Hulaku Khan's army panics. At this time, Nasreddin and the khan sat quietly and watched the panic in the army. Nasreddin Khan says: "Sovereign, we are sitting quietly because we know the reason for the sound coming from the rocks. And the army is in a state of excitement because it does not know this. If we know in advance the nature of the events happening in the sky, such peace will always reign on earth." Nasreddin's words convinced Hulaku Khan so much that he agreed to the construction of the observatory and left 20 thousand dinars for this purpose. Later, the great scientist employed more than a hundred people working in the observatory. Alima also achieves a permanent freeze was paid. (1)

Many researchers consider Nasreddin Tusi, first of all, a mathematician. His works played an important role in the development of geometry and trigonometry not only in the East, but also in Europe. "Euclid" and "Description of the Beginning" published in Rome in 1594 and then translated into Latin did a great job in spreading Tusi's ideas in Europe. "Treatise on Complete Quadrilaterals", written by the scientist in five books, is famous as the work that played an important role in the development of trigonometry in Europe. For the first time in the history of world science, trigonometry is treated as an independent field of science in this work. This treatise has been translated into English, Russian and French. Among Nasreddin's researches in the field of algebra, the method of fattening all degrees and the Binomial formula are more well known. In addition, his numerous works on scientific history, mineralogy, physics, medicine, economics, geography, music and, of course, astronomy are noteworthy. Among them are History of Bagdad, Treatise on the Reflection and Refraction of Light, Euclidean Optics, Treatise on the Study of the Rainbow, Book on Precious Stones, Laws of Medicine, Treatise on Public Finance, Happy selection of days" (astrology) and other works can be mentioned. His works are scattered around the world. They can be found in museums and libraries of Baku, Paris, Berlin, Vienna, Oxford, Cambridge, Leipzig, Munich, Florence, Cairo, Istanbul, Moscow, St. Petersburg, Kazan. Many of Nasreddin's works are still waiting for their researchers.

Nasreddin Tusi wrote: "If you suffer in doing good work. Suffering passes, good remains, if you do evil and enjoy it, pleasure goes, evil remains."

Nasreddin Tusi (1201-1274) considered morality to be wealth and noted that it is not innate. He said: "If character was innate, then intelligent people would not advise on the upbringing of their children and the refinement, strengthening and habituation of the morals of young people, and they would not engage in it themselves."

The result

In general, medieval Eastern philosophy constitutes a special stage in world philosophical thought.

The Middle Ages, characterized in the West as a period of "ignorance and ignorance", was a period of flourishing of enlightened ideas and scientific knowledge in Eastern countries. Eastern philosophers and thinkers have put forward exhausted scientific and philosophical concepts along with religious and philosophical teachings in their full content works reflecting the spiritual life of the time.

In general, the teaching of medieval Azerbaijani philosophers to students in physics education in grades VII-IX has an important role in strengthening their knowledge and skills regarding the conduct of mental operations, the types and importance of activities.

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